

L1-L2 vowel relations in English monophthong production by Hijazi Arabic learners: Evidence from interactive phonetic training

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Second-language (L2) vowel production depends on how learners relate non-native vowel categories to their first-language (L1) phonetic system, yet little is known about how vowel-specific difficulty and improvement can be explained within an L2 speech learning model. This study examined English monophthong production by Hijazi Arabic-speaking learners through Flege's Speech Learning Model and compared mobile-based Interactive Phonetic Training (IPT) with Print-Based Phonetic Instruction (PBI). Forty Hijazi Arabic-speaking English majors completed pre-test and post-test production tasks involving eleven English monophthongs. Productions were analysed through vowel-specific confusion matrices and modelled using mixed-effects logistic regression. The results showed that learners had the greatest difficulty with vowels lacking direct Hijazi Arabic equivalents, especially /ε/, /ɜ:/, /ɔ:/, /ɒ/, and /ʌ/. The IPT group showed significantly greater post-test improvement than the PBI group, particularly for these difficult vowels. The findings suggest that interactive phonetic training can reduce L1-based substitutions and support more accurate L2 vowel production.

Keywords: English Monophthong Production; Hijazi Arabic; Interactive Phonetic Training; L2 Phonetics; Speech Learning Model

1. Introduction

Pronunciation is a central component of second-language (L2) speech development because it influences intelligibility and communicative effectiveness (Morley, 1991). Among pronunciation elements, vowels are particularly important because they form syllable nuclei and contribute to lexical contrasts, stress patterns, and temporal organisation in speech (Ladefoged & Johnson, 2010). Small differences in vowel quality can change meaning; for example, *ship* /ʃɪp/ and *sheep* /ʃi:p/ differ primarily in vowel quality and duration. Inaccurate vowel production may therefore lead to misunderstandings or confusion. This difficulty becomes more pronounced when L2 learners fail to produce vowel contrasts that are absent or differently organised in their first language (L1). Vowels also present challenges for many L2 learners because their quality depends on subtle distinctions in tongue height, tongue backness, lip rounding, and duration (Ladefoged & Johnson, 2010; Roach, 2009). For

these reasons, vowel production is a central issue in L2 phonetics and phonology. Accurate vowel production not only enhances intelligibility but also reflects the learner's ability to establish target-like L2 phonetic categories. These difficulties become particularly evident in the case of English and Arabic, as the two systems differ substantially in both size and quality.

For Arabic-speaking learners of English, these systemic differences are especially relevant to vowel production (Munro, 1993). Saudi L2 learners of English often face difficulties in producing English vowels (Evans & Alshangiti, 2018). A major source of these challenges is the difference between the vowel inventories of English and Arabic (Almurashi et al., 2023). English also has a richer vowel inventory than Arabic, which increases the number of contrasts that Arabic-speaking learners must acquire. In particular, English has 11 monophthongs: /u:/, /ɜ:/, /ʊ/, /ɪ/, /ɛ/, /ʌ/, /æ/, /ɒ/, /ɑ:/, /ɔ:/, and /i:/ (Wells, 1982). Birjandi and Salmani Nodoushan (2005) also include /ə/ in their English vowel chart.

In contrast, Arabic has a more limited vowel system (Al-Ani, 1970; Watson, 2002). Hijazi Arabic, which is the focus of the present study, is commonly described as having three short vowels /u, i, a/, three long vowels /u:, i:, a:/, and two long mid vowels /e:/ and /o:/ (Jarrah, 1993). Thus, several English vowels have no direct equivalent in Hijazi Arabic, including mid-front vowels such as /ɛ/, central vowels such as /ɜ:/ and /ʌ/, rounded back vowels such as /ɔ:/, and open back vowels such as /ɒ/. These inventory contrasts may lead learners to assimilate unfamiliar English vowels to the closest L1 categories, which may reduce contrastiveness or lead to inaccurate production (Flege et al., 1997). Within Flege's Speech Learning Model (SLM), these difficulties can be interpreted through the distinction between 'new' and 'similar' L2 sounds. Some English vowels may be sufficiently different from L1 categories, whereas others may be treated as close to existing L1 vowels (Bohn & Flege, 1992; Flege, 1995). This framework is therefore useful for explaining production difficulties and for understanding how learners develop phonetic contrasts that are absent or less clearly specified in their L1 vowel system (Flege, 1995).

In Saudi Arabia, pupils begin learning English at an early stage in primary school. Despite this curricular exposure, instruction often gives greater attention to grammar, vocabulary, and written exercises than to oral practice (Alshahrani, 2016; Jahara & Abdelrady, 2021). As a result, many L2 learners develop basic reading and writing skills but continue to face difficulty with accurate speech production. Pronunciation is rarely taught systematically, and learners often rely on the teacher's model or on sounds from their first language. This may lead to persistent vowel errors, especially in English vowels that have no direct equivalent in Hijazi Arabic. Traditional classroom approaches often rely on printed textbooks and worksheets, which provide

limited support for vowel articulation and auditory-phonetic awareness (Alresheed et al., 2017). Learners may therefore receive little exposure to clear articulatory models, corrective feedback, and repeated production practice (Fouz-González, 2020; Haggag, 2018; Khalil, 2022). Targeted phonetic training may address these limitations because it combines auditory input, articulatory explanation, production practice, and feedback. Mobile phonetic training may be particularly useful because it can direct learners' attention to vowel quality, articulatory position, auditory models, and corrective feedback (Fatimah, 2021; Miqawati, 2020; Stoughton & Kang, 2024). Such input may help learners produce difficult English vowels more accurately, especially vowels that are close to or absent from Hijazi Arabic vowel categories.

Previous L2 speech learning research has shown that phonetic training can improve learners' pronunciation, particularly when training provides auditory input, articulatory support, production practice, and feedback. However, much of this work has focused on whether learners improve after training, with less attention to how vowel production difficulties and post-training improvement can be explained within an L2 speech learning model. Therefore, the present study addresses this gap by examining whether mobile-based Interactive Phonetic Training (IPT) supports English vowel production among Hijazi Arabic-speaking learners, compared with Print-Based Phonetic Instruction (PBI), and by interpreting vowel-specific difficulties and improvement through the SLM framework. The study also provides a fine-grained analysis of vowel production using vowel-specific confusion matrices to identify which English vowel categories are most difficult and which show the greatest improvement after training. In addition, mixed-effects logistic regression is used to examine changes in vowel production accuracy while accounting for learner- and vowel-level variation. The study addresses the following research questions.

- (1) Which English vowel categories are most difficult for Hijazi Arabic-speaking L2 learners to produce, and how can these difficulties be explained in relation to the L1–L2 vowel category relationship?
- (2) Does mobile-based IPT lead to greater improvement in Hijazi Arabic-speaking learners' production of English monophthongs than PBI?
- (3) Which English vowel categories show the largest post-training gains, and to what extent can these gains be interpreted through the SLM?

2. Background

2.1. The speech learning model

Flege's SLM provides the theoretical framework for the present study. The model explains L2 speech acquisition in relation to the interaction between L1 and L2 phonetic categories. It proposes that adult L2 learners do not

completely lose the ability to acquire new speech sounds. Instead, L2 speech learning remains possible across the lifespan, although it is strongly influenced by learners' previous experience with the L1 sound system (Flege, 1995). A central assumption of the SLM is that L2 and L1 sounds exist within a shared phonetic space. When learners encounter an L2 sound, they compare it with the closest sound in their L1 system. If the L2 sound is perceived as sufficiently different from existing L1 categories, learners may establish a new phonetic category for it. However, if the L2 sound is perceived as similar to an existing L1 category, learners might classify it as equivalent to that L1 sound. Flege refers to this process as 'equivalence classification'. When equivalence classification occurs, the formation of a separate L2 category may be blocked or delayed. The SLM therefore posits that L2 sounds that are close to existing L1 categories may be difficult to produce accurately because learners may rely on the nearest L1 category rather than establish a separate target-like L2 category. As a result, their production may continue to be influenced by the L1 sound system. In contrast, L2 sounds that are clearly different from L1 sounds may be easier to separate because learners are more likely to recognise them as new categories. These assumptions make the SLM particularly useful for explaining why some L2 sounds are produced more accurately than others. The SLM is directly relevant to the present study because English includes several vowel categories that do not have direct equivalents in Hijazi Arabic, such as /ɛ/, /ɜ:/, /ɔ:/, and /ɒ/. From an SLM perspective, Hijazi Arabic learners may rely on nearby L1 vowel categories when they produce unfamiliar English vowels. Therefore, the model provides a useful framework for interpreting vowel substitutions, production difficulties, and post-training changes in English vowel accuracy.

2.2. Previous studies on technology-mediated phonetic training

Previous research in English as a foreign language (EFL) context has shown growing interest in technology-mediated phonetic training for improving segmental accuracy, particularly in relation to English vowels. Although these studies vary in context, design, and instructional tools, they generally show that vowel learning benefits from a combination of auditory input, visual or articulatory support, repeated production practice, and feedback. These features are important because English vowels often require learners to attend to fine phonetic differences in vowel quality, tongue height, tongue position, and lip rounding. For example, Haggag (2018) examined *HPhonetics*, a mobile phonetics platform, with Egyptian pre-service EFL teachers and found statistically significant gains in segmental features, especially vowel classification. Although the study focused on phonetic achievement rather than only production, it suggests that structured mobile-based phonetic training can strengthen learners' awareness of English vowel categories.

Similarly, Fouz-González (2020) investigated *English File Pronunciation* with Spanish university students and reported improvement in vowel production accuracy. This improvement was linked to training that included repeated phonetic practice, auditory models, and articulatory guidance. Together, these studies suggest that technology-mediated phonetic training can support vowel learning when it helps learners connect sound, symbol, and articulation. Other studies have emphasised the role of feedback and repeated production practice. Miqawati (2020) examined *TFLAT English Pronunciation* in a first-semester pronunciation class and showed that training involving articulatory explanation, structured practice, self-checking, voice recording, and feedback supported learners' pronunciation development. Similarly, Fatimah (2021) found that Android-based pronunciation tools with speech-recognition activities helped Indonesian undergraduates improve their English vowel accuracy. These studies indicate that technology is most useful when it does not simply present pronunciation information, but also gives learners opportunities to listen, produce, compare, monitor, and adjust their speech.

Research in the Saudi EFL context is more limited, but existing studies also point to the value of targeted phonetic training. Khalil (2022) examined Saudi English majors' learning of English vowels using the mobile application *English Pronunciation*, and found statistically significant improvement after the intervention. This finding suggests that focused mobile-assisted phonetic instruction can help address vowel-related difficulties among Saudi learners. More recently, Almutairi and Alghammas (2025) examined *ELSA Speak* with Saudi secondary school learners and found that learners who received technology-mediated pronunciation practice made greater gains than those who received traditional instruction, particularly in overall speaking and pronunciation accuracy. These findings support the view that interactive tools with auditory feedback can improve pronunciation learning.

3. Method

This study was conducted with 40 ($N = 40$) sophomore English majors at Taibah University in Saudi Arabia. All participants were native speakers of Hijazi Arabic and were aged 20 to 27 years ($M = 21.3$, $Md = 21$)— M indicates the mean age, and Md indicates the median age. None reported hearing or speech disorders. Participants were randomly assigned to two equal groups: 20 in the IPT group and 20 in the PBI group. The IPT group received auditory, articulatory, and feedback-based vowel training, whereas the PBI group received printed phonetic materials and teacher modelling. Participants were asked to produce 11 English vowels: /ɑ:/, /æ/, /i:/, /ɛ/, /ɜ:/, /ɪ/, /ɔ:/, /ʊ/, /ʌ/, /u:/, and /ʊ/. Each vowel was elicited in an /hVd/ context to control the consonantal environment. Each participant produced each target vowel three times in the pre-test and three times in the post-test. Because each group

included 20 participants, each vowel contributed 60 tokens per group at each testing time. Each group therefore produced 660 vowel tokens at the pre-test and 660 at the post-test, calculated as 20 participants \times 11 vowels \times 3 repetitions. Across both groups and both testing times, the dataset contained 2,640 vowel tokens.

The study employed a pre-test/post-test design over seven-week phonetic training period. During this period, the IPT group received structured vowel training through a mobile-based phonetic training application, whereas the PBI group used printed phonetic materials and teacher modelling without interactive auditory-visual feedback. Both groups received the same amount of training time: 12 sessions over seven weeks, with each session lasting 40 minutes. At the end of the training period, both groups completed a post-test that was identical to the pre-test. The IPT group used *Voices*, a mobile-based phonetic training application designed to support English vowel production. The application presented IPA vowel symbols, high-quality audio models, and male and female voice models. It also provided animated two-dimensional visualisations of tongue, lip, and jaw movements. These visualisations linked auditory input to articulatory gestures that are often difficult to demonstrate through printed materials alone. Learners were able to record their own speech and compare it with target models through the application's feedback system, which provided auditory and visual comparison. In addition, *Voices* included articulatory diagrams, acoustic displays, and lexical examples. Together, these features connected auditory models, acoustic information, phonetic symbols, and articulatory movement.

Two trained raters with expertise in English phonetics judged the vowel productions. The recordings were anonymised and presented in random order. The raters were blinded to participant group and testing time, and they identified the perceived English vowel category for each production. Inter-rater reliability was assessed using Cohen's *kappa* before disagreement resolution, with the result showing almost perfect agreement, $\kappa = .89$. Any disagreements were resolved through discussion, and the final agreed classifications were used in the analysis. These classifications were entered into confusion matrices to calculate vowel production accuracy. Vowel-specific accuracy was calculated by dividing the number of correctly classified productions of each target vowel by the total number of productions for that vowel in the relevant group and testing time, then multiplying by 100. Because each target vowel contributed 60 productions per group at each testing time, each row of the confusion matrix was based on 60 productions. The number of productions assigned to each rater-response category was divided by 60 and converted into a percentage. Percentages were rounded to the nearest whole number for presentation. Overall group accuracy was calculated by dividing

the total number of correct vowel productions across the 11 vowels by the total number of vowel tokens for that group and testing time.

For statistical analysis, vowel production accuracy was coded as a binary variable. A production was coded as 1 when the agreed rater classification matched the target vowel and as 0 when it did not. Because the dataset included repeated productions from the same participants, a mixed-effects logistic regression model was used. The model included Group, Time, the Group \times Time interaction, and Target Vowel as fixed effects. Group had two levels: Interactive Phonetic Training and Print-Based Phonetic Instruction. Time had two levels: pre-test and post-test. Target Vowel included the eleven English monophthongs. Participant was included as a random intercept to account for repeated productions by the same learners. The Group \times Time interaction was the primary effect of interest because it tested whether improvement from pre-test to post-test differed between the IPT and PBI groups. Fixed effects were evaluated using likelihood-ratio *chi-square* tests. For the significant Group \times Time interaction, the model coefficient, standard error, and z value were reported to describe the direction and size of the group difference in improvement. Model-estimated accuracy percentages were reported by group and time to describe changes in vowel production accuracy after training.

4. Results

This section has three subsections. The first subsection presents the results of the PBI group, with pre-test and post-test confusion matrices. The second subsection presents the results of the IPT group, with pre-test and post-test confusion matrices. The third subsection compares pre-test and post-test vowel production accuracy within each group and reports a mixed-effects logistic regression that tests whether improvement differed between the IPT and PBI groups.

4.1. Print-based phonetic instruction group

The results of the PBI group revealed clear patterns in English vowel production. In the pre-test, Hijazi L2 learners showed high accuracy for some vowel categories but clear difficulty with others, especially mid, central, and back vowels (see Figure 1 below).

The vowel /ɑ:/ was produced correctly in 85% of cases, while the remaining 15% of productions were classified as /æ/. The vowel /æ/ showed the same overall accuracy, with 85% correct production. Its errors were distributed between /ɑ:/ at 4% and /ʌ/ at 11%. Thus, both low vowels showed relatively high accuracy in the PBI pre-test, with most errors limited to neighbouring low or central vowel categories. The high front vowels also showed high pre-test

accuracy. The vowel /i:/ was produced correctly in 84% of cases. Its main substitution was /ɪ/, which accounted for 15% of productions, while only 1% was classified as /ɛ/.

Figure 1.

Pre-Test Vowel Confusion Matrix with Production Accuracy Percentages for the Print-Based Phonetic Instruction Group

The vowel /ɪ/ had the highest accuracy in the matrix, with 90% correct production. Its errors were limited to /i:/ at 7% and /ɛ/ at 3%. These results show that the high front vowel pair /i:/-/ɪ/ was produced with relatively high accuracy, although some overlap occurred between the tense and lax members of the pair. The mid and central vowels had lower accuracy in the PBI pre-test. The vowel /ɛ/ was produced correctly in 50% of cases. The remaining productions were distributed across several vowel categories: /ɪ/ at 24%, /i:/ at 10%, /ɜ:/ at 7%, /ʌ/ at 7%, and /æ/ at 2%. The vowel /ɜ:/ also showed 50% correct production. Its errors were mainly classified as /i:/ at 25%, followed by /ɛ/ at 13% and /ɪ/ at 12%. The central vowel /ʌ/ reached 59% accuracy. Its largest substitution was /æ/, which accounted for 34% of productions. Smaller proportions were classified as /ʊ/ at 5%, /ɑ:/ at 1%, and /ɛ/ at 1%. The back

vowels also showed lower accuracy than the high front and high back vowels. The vowel /ɔ:/ was produced correctly in 52% of cases. Its errors were classified as /u:/ at 22%, /ɒ/ at 17%, and /ʊ/ at 9%. The vowel /ɒ/ had 50% accuracy. Its substitutions were distributed across /ʊ/ at 21%, /u:/ at 16%, /ɔ:/ at 11%, and /ʌ/ at 2%. These values show several off-diagonal responses within the back vowel region of the matrix. In contrast, the high back vowels showed higher levels of correct production. The vowel /u:/ was produced correctly in 87% of cases, with errors classified as /ʊ/ at 10% and /ɔ:/ at 3%. The vowel /ʊ/ reached 85% accuracy, with 10% of productions classified as /u:/ and 5% as /ɒ/. Overall, the PBI pre-test matrix shows higher accuracy for /ɪ/, /u:/, /ɑ:/, /æ/, /ʊ/, and /i:/, while lower accuracy was found for /ɛ/, /ɜ:/, /ɒ/, /ɔ:/, and /ʌ/.

Figure 2.

Post-Test Vowel Confusion Matrix with Production Accuracy Percentages for the Print-Based Phonetic Instruction Group

In the post-test, Figure 2 (above) shows higher accuracy values than those reported in the pre-test for the PBI group. The vowel /ɑ:/ was produced

correctly in 90% of cases, while 10% of productions were classified as /æ/. The vowel /æ/ also reached 90% accuracy. Its errors were distributed between /ʌ/ at 7% and /ɑ:/ at 3%. These two low vowels therefore showed the same post-test accuracy value in the PBI group. The high front vowels also showed high post-test accuracy. The vowel /i:/ reached 88% accuracy, with 11% of productions classified as /ɪ/ and 1% as /ɛ/. The vowel /ɪ/ reached 93% accuracy, which was the highest value in the PBI post-test matrix. Its errors were limited to /i:/ at 5% and /ɛ/ at 2%. Compared with the other front vowels, /ɪ/ had the highest correct classification rate, while /ɛ/ had the lowest. The vowel /ɛ/ reached 65% accuracy in the post-test. The remaining productions were distributed across several vowel categories: /ɪ/ at 17%, /i:/ at 7%, /ɜ:/ at 5%, /ʌ/ at 5%, and /æ/ at 1%. The vowel /ɜ:/ showed a similar post-test value, with 64% correct production. Its errors were classified as /i:/ at 18%, /ɛ/ at 9%, and /ɪ/ at 9%. Among the front and central vowel categories, /ɛ/ and /ɜ:/ had lower accuracy than /i:/ and /ɪ/. The back vowels showed mid-range post-test accuracy values. The vowel /ɔ:/ was produced correctly in 65% of cases. Its errors were classified as /u:/ at 16%, /ɒ/ at 12%, and /ʊ/ at 7%. The vowel /ɒ/ reached 62% accuracy. Its substitutions were distributed across /ʊ/ at 16%, /u:/ at 12%, /ɔ:/ at 8%, and /ʌ/ at 2%. Within the back vowel set, /ɔ:/ and /ɒ/ had lower correct classification rates than /u:/ and /ʊ/. The central vowel /ʌ/ reached 70% accuracy. Its main substitution was /æ/, which accounted for 25% of productions. Smaller proportions were classified as /ʊ/ at 3%, /ɑ:/ at 1%, and /ɛ/ at 1%. The high back vowels showed higher accuracy values than /ɔ:/ and /ɒ/. The vowel /u:/ was produced correctly in 90% of cases, with 8% of productions classified as /ʊ/ and 2% as /ɔ:/. The vowel /ʊ/ reached 88% accuracy, with errors classified as /u:/ at 8% and /ɒ/ at 4%. Overall, the PBI post-test matrix shows the highest accuracy for /ɪ/ at 93%, followed by /ɑ:/, /æ/, and /u:/ at 90%. The vowels /i:/ and /ʊ/ followed at 88%. The lowest accuracy values were found for /ɒ/ at 62%, /ɜ:/ at 64%, /ɛ/ and /ɔ:/ at 65%, and /ʌ/ at 70%. Compared with the pre-test, all eleven vowels showed higher correct classification values in the post-test.

4.2. Interactive phonetic training group

The IPT group showed mixed performance in the pre-test, with high accuracy for some vowel categories and persistent difficulty with others, especially mid, central, and back vowels (see Figure 3 below).

The vowel /ɑ:/ was produced correctly in 82% of cases. Most of its errors were classified as /æ/, which accounted for 16% of productions. Smaller errors were classified as /ɛ/ at 1% and /ɪ/ at 1%. The vowel /æ/ reached 81% accuracy. Its errors were classified as /ɑ:/ at 8%, /ʌ/ at 10%, and /ɛ/ at 1%. Thus, both /ɑ:/ and /æ/ had accuracy values above 80% in the IPT pre-test. The high front vowels also had relatively high accuracy values. The vowel /i:/ was produced

correctly in 85% of cases. Its main substitution was /ɪ/, which accounted for 13% of productions. Smaller proportions were classified as /ɛ/ at 1% and /ɜ:/ at 1%. The vowel /ɪ/ reached 89% accuracy, which was the highest value in the IPT pre-test matrix. Its errors were classified as /i:/ at 7%, /ɛ/ at 2%, and /ɜ:/ at 2%. Within the front vowel set, /i:/ and /ɪ/ had higher accuracy values than /ɛ/ and /ɜ:/. The mid vowels had lower accuracy values in the IPT pre-test. The vowel /ɛ/ had 45% accuracy, which was the lowest value in the matrix. Its errors were distributed across several vowel categories: /ɪ/ at 26%, /ʌ/ at 9%, /i:/ at 8%, /ɜ:/ at 8%, and /æ/ at 4%. The vowel /ɜ:/ reached 51% accuracy.

Figure 3.

Pre-Test Vowel Confusion Matrix with Production Accuracy Percentages for the Interactive Phonetic Training Group

Its largest substitution was /i:/, which accounted for 27% of productions. Other errors were classified as /ɛ/ at 10%, /ɪ/ at 10%, and /ʌ/ at 2%. The back vowels /ɔ:/ and /ɒ/ also had low accuracy values. The vowel /ɔ:/ was produced correctly in 50% of cases. Its errors were classified as /u:/ at 25%, /ɒ/ at 13%, and /ʊ/ at 12%. The vowel /ɒ/ also reached 50% accuracy. Its

substitutions were distributed across /u:/ at 19%, /ʊ/ at 19%, /ɔ:/ at 10%, /æ/ at 1%, and /ʌ/ at 1%. These two vowels therefore had the same correct classification rate in the IPT pre-test. The central vowel /ʌ/ reached 60% accuracy. Its main substitution was /æ/, which accounted for 32% of productions. Smaller proportions were classified as /ɑ:/ at 3%, /ɛ/ at 3%, and /ʊ/ at 2%. The high back vowels showed higher accuracy values than /ɔ:/ and /ɒ/. The vowel /u:/ was produced correctly in 86% of cases, with 12% of productions classified as /ʊ/ and 2% as /ɔ:/. The vowel /ʊ/ reached 84% accuracy, with errors classified as /u:/ at 14% and /ɒ/ at 2%. Overall, the IPT pre-test matrix shows the highest accuracy for /ɪ/ at 89%, followed by /u:/ at 86%, /i:/ at 85%, /ʊ/ at 84%, /ɑ:/ at 82%, and /æ/ at 81%. Lower accuracy values were found for /ʌ/ at 60%, /ɜ:/ at 51%, /ɔ:/ and /ɒ/ at 50%, and /ɛ/ at 45%.

The post-test results of the IPT group are presented in Figure 4. The matrix shows higher correct classification values across all eleven vowels compared with the IPT pre-test. The vowel /ɑ:/ was produced correctly in 95% of cases. The only substitution for this vowel was /æ/, which accounted for 5% of productions. The vowel /æ/ reached 93% accuracy. Its errors were classified as /ʌ/ at 5% and /ɑ:/ at 2%. Both low vowels therefore had post-test accuracy values above 90%. The high front vowels also showed high post-test accuracy. The vowel /i:/ reached 92% accuracy, with the remaining 8% of productions classified as /ɪ/. The vowel /ɪ/ had the highest accuracy value in the IPT post-test matrix, with 96% correct production. Its errors were limited to /i:/ at 3% and /ɛ/ at 1%. Within the front vowel set, /ɪ/ had the highest correct classification rate, followed by /i:/, /ɛ/, and /ɜ:/. The vowel /ɛ/ reached 84% accuracy in the post-test. Its errors were distributed across /ɪ/ at 8%, /i:/ at 3%, /ɜ:/ at 2%, /ʌ/ at 2%, and /æ/ at 1%. The vowel /ɜ:/ was produced correctly in 82% of cases. Its substitutions were classified as /i:/ at 9%, /ɛ/ at 5%, and /ɪ/ at 4%. Although /ɛ/ and /ɜ:/ had lower accuracy values than /i:/ and /ɪ/, both vowels reached accuracy values above 80% in the post-test. The back vowels /ɔ:/ and /ɒ/ also showed higher post-test values than in the pre-test. The vowel /ɔ:/ reached 80% accuracy. Its errors were classified as /u:/ at 9%, /ɒ/ at 7%, and /ʊ/ at 4%. The vowel /ɒ/ was produced correctly in 78% of cases. Its substitutions were distributed across /ʊ/ at 9%, /u:/ at 7%, /ɔ:/ at 5%, and /ʌ/ at 1%. Among the back vowels, /u:/ and /ʊ/ had higher accuracy values than /ɔ:/ and /ɒ/. The central vowel /ʌ/ reached 81% accuracy. Its main substitution was /æ/, which accounted for 17% of productions. A smaller proportion was classified as /ʊ/ at 2%. The high back vowels showed high levels of correct production. The vowel /u:/ reached 94% accuracy, with 5% of productions classified as /ʊ/ and 1% as /ɔ:/. The vowel /ʊ/ reached 93% accuracy, with errors classified as /u:/ at 5% and /ɒ/ at 2%. Overall, the IPT post-test matrix shows the highest accuracy for /ɪ/ at 96%, followed by /ɑ:/ at

95%, /u:/ at 94%, /æ/ and /ʊ/ at 93%, and /i:/ at 92%. The remaining vowels also had accuracy values above 75%, with /ɛ/ at 84%, /ɜ:/ at 82%, /ʌ/ at 81%, /ɔ:/ at 80%, and /ɒ/ at 78%. Compared with the IPT pre-test, all eleven vowels had higher correct classification values in the post-test.

Figure 4.

Post-Test Vowel Confusion Matrix with Production Accuracy Percentages for the Interactive Phonetic Training Group

4.3. Comparison

This subsection compares the IPT and PBI groups in terms of pre-test and post-test vowel production accuracy. It first describes the overall change in accuracy across the two groups and then reports the mixed-effects logistic regression, which tested whether improvement differed between groups. Figure 5 presents the distribution of vowel production accuracy across the eleven English monophthongs for each group at pre-test and post-test.

Figure 5.
Boxplots of English Vowel Production Accuracy for the Interactive Phonetic Training group and the Print-Based Phonetic Instruction group at Pre-Test and Post-Test

Each box in figure 5 summarises the distribution across the 11 vowels; whiskers represent the range. The dashed line inside each box represents the mean.

At pre-test, the two groups had very similar mean accuracy scores. The IPT group began with an average vowel production accuracy of 69.5%, while the PBI group began with a slightly higher mean of 70.5%. The pre-test distributions also showed a wide range of accuracy scores in both groups. In the IPT group, pre-test scores ranged from about 45% to 89%. In the PBI group, pre-test scores ranged from about 50% to 90%. This pattern shows that both groups included vowels with high pre-test accuracy as well as vowels with much lower pre-test accuracy. At post-test, both groups showed higher mean accuracy, but the increase was larger in the IPT group. The IPT group increased from 69.5% to 88%, which represents a gain of 18.5%. The PBI group increased from 70.5% to 78.6%, which represents a gain of 8.1%. The post-test range also differed between the two groups. In the IPT group, the scores ranged from 78% to 96%, while in the PBI group, they ranged from 62% to 93%. Thus, the lowest post-test accuracy in the IPT group was higher than the lowest post-test accuracy in the PBI group. The IPT post-test distribution was also more concentrated in the upper accuracy range, whereas the PBI post-test distribution remained wider.

Figure 6.

Percentage Gains in English Vowel Production Accuracy from Pre-Test to Post-Test for Each Vowel in the Interactive Phonetic Training Group and the Print-Based Phonetic Instruction Group

Dashed horizontal lines represent the group means.

A closer comparison of vowel production accuracy is presented in Figure 6 (above). The IPT group showed gains for all eleven vowels, with an average gain of 18.5%. The PBI group also showed gains for all eleven vowels, with an average gain of 8.2%. Thus, the average gain in the IPT group was 10.3% higher than that of the PBI group. For the low and low-front vowels, the IPT group showed larger gains than the PBI group. The vowel /ɑ:/ improved by 13% in the IPT group and by 5% in the PBI group, a difference of 8%. The vowel /æ/ improved by 12% in the IPT group and by 5% in the PBI group, a difference of 7%. For the high front vowel /i:/, the difference between the two groups was smaller, with a gain of 7% in the IPT group and 5% in the PBI group. The vowel /ɪ/ also showed a smaller difference, with a gain of 7% in the IPT group and 3% in the PBI group. The largest gains in the IPT group were found for /ɛ/, /ɜ:/, /ɔ:/, /ɒ/, and /ʌ/. The vowel /ɛ/ showed the highest gain, with an increase of 38% in the IPT group, compared with 15% in the PBI group. This represents a between-group difference of 23%. The vowel /ɜ:/ improved by 30% in the IPT group and by 13% in the PBI group, a difference of 17%. The vowel /ɔ:/ showed the same pattern, with a gain of 30% in the IPT group and 13% in the PBI group. The vowel /ɒ/ improved by 28% in the IPT group and by 12% in the PBI group, a difference of 16%. The central vowel /ʌ/ improved by 22% in the IPT group and by 12% in the PBI group, a difference of 10%. For the high back vowels, the

gains were lower than those reported for /ε/, /ɜ:/, /ɔ:/, /ʊ/, and /ʌ/. The vowel /u:/ improved by 7% in the IPT group and by 3% in the PBI group, a difference of 4%. The vowel /ʊ/ improved by 10% in the IPT group and by 3% in the PBI group, a difference of 7%. Overall, Figure 6 (above) shows that the IPT group had larger gains than the PBI group for every vowel category. The smallest between-group difference was found for /i:/ at 2%, while the largest difference was found for /ε/ at 23%. The remaining between-group differences ranged from 4% to 17%.

These descriptive results are followed by the mixed-effects logistic regression, which tested whether the change from pre-test to post-test differed significantly between the IPT and PBI groups.

Table 1
Results of the Mixed-Effects Logistic Regression Model Predicting Vowel Production Accuracy

Effect	χ^2	df	p value
Group	0.15	1	.700
Time	13	1	< .001
Target Vowel	240.56	10	< .001
Group × Time	15.29	1	< .001

A mixed-effects logistic regression was conducted to test whether the change in vowel production accuracy differed between the two groups (see Table 1). As mentioned in the methodology, vowel production accuracy was coded as a binary outcome, with correct productions coded as 1 and incorrect productions coded as 0. The model included Group, Time, Target Vowel, and the Group × Time interaction as fixed effects. Participant was included as a random intercept to account for repeated productions from the same learners. The effect of Group was not significant, $\chi^2(1) = 0.15$, $p = .700$. This result shows no significant overall difference between the IPT and PBI groups in the model. The effect of Time was significant, $\chi^2(1) = 13.00$, $p < .001$. This result shows a significant change in vowel production accuracy from pre-test to post-test across the two groups. The effect of Target Vowel was also significant, $\chi^2(10) = 240.56$, $p < .001$. This result shows that accuracy differed across the eleven English monophthongs. The Group × Time interaction was significant, $\chi^2(1) = 15.29$, $p < .001$. This interaction tested whether the change from pre-test to post-test differed between the IPT and PBI groups. The model coefficient for the interaction was $\beta = 0.80$, $SE = 0.20$, $z = 3.91$, $p < .001$. This result is consistent with the results in Figure 7, where the IPT group showed an average gain of 18.5%, compared with 8.2% in the PBI group. Together, the regression results show a significant effect of Time, a significant effect of Target Vowel,

and a significant Group \times Time interaction. The only non-significant effect was Group, $\chi^2(1) = 0.15, p = .700$.

5. Discussion

The findings provide evidence about L2 English vowel production by Hijazi Arabic learners and show clear differences across vowel categories. In the pre-test, both the IPT and PBI groups showed difficulty with several English vowels, particularly / ε /, / $z:$ /, / $ɔ:$ /, / υ /, and / Λ /. These vowels were among the least accurate categories before instruction, and they also showed several substitutions in the confusion matrices. This pattern is important because these vowels do not have direct equivalents in Hijazi Arabic. As a result, learners appeared to produce them in ways that were close to existing or more familiar vowel categories. For example, / ε / was often classified as / i /, / $z:$ / was often classified as / $i:$ /, and the back vowels / $ɔ:$ / and / υ / were often classified as / $u:$ / and / u /. The central vowel / Λ / was also frequently classified as / æ /, which shows another area of overlap between the English target vowel and a nearby vowel category. These substitution patterns are consistent with cross-linguistic phonetic transfer and can be interpreted through Flege's Speech Learning Model. According to the SLM, L2 sounds are not learned in isolation from the L1 system. Instead, learners relate new L2 sounds to the phonetic categories that already exist in their L1. When an L2 sound is sufficiently different from an L1 sound, the learner may establish a separate phonetic category for it. However, when an L2 sound is perceived as similar to an L1 category, equivalence classification may prevent or delay the formation of a distinct L2 category (Flege, 1995). In the present study, the lower pre-test accuracy for / ε /, / $z:$ /, / $ɔ:$ /, / υ /, and / Λ / suggests that these vowels were not yet fully separated from nearby vowel categories in the learners' production system. The errors were not random across the vowel space. Rather, they were concentrated in phonetically related areas, such as front vowel substitutions for / ε / and / $z:$ /, back vowel substitutions for / $ɔ:$ / and / υ /, and low-central overlap for / Λ /. This supports the view that L1-L2 vowel relations shaped learners' production accuracy before training.

The post-test results show that this pattern changed after instruction, especially in the IPT group. On average, the IPT group improved by 18.5%, whereas the PBI group improved by about 8.2%. The largest gains in the IPT group appeared in vowels that were least accurate at pre-test. The vowel / ε / improved by 38%, / $z:$ / by 30%, / $ɔ:$ / by 30%, and / υ / by 28%. These gains show that the categories with the greatest initial difficulty also showed the largest improvement after interactive training. The mixed-effects logistic regression also showed a significant Group \times Time interaction, which confirms that the change from pre-test to post-test differed between the two groups. The IPT group showed greater improvement in vowel production accuracy than the

PBI group, both in the descriptive results and in the statistical model. From an SLM perspective, these results suggest that interactive phonetic training may have helped learners reduce reliance on nearby L1 vowel categories associated with equivalence classification. The IPT condition provided several types of support at the same time: auditory models, production practice, articulatory visualisations, and feedback. These features may have helped learners notice the phonetic distance between the English target vowel and the vowel category that they had used as a substitute. For example, repeated exposure to /ɛ/ with an auditory model and articulatory display may have helped learners distinguish it more clearly from /ɪ/ and /i:/. Similarly, practice with /ɔ:/ and /ɒ/ may have helped learners reduce substitutions with /u:/ and /ʊ/. The use of feedback may also have helped learners compare their own production with the target model and adjust their production over time. The improvement in the IPT group is particularly important because the most difficult vowels were not simply vowels with low pre-test scores; they were also vowels that lacked direct Hijazi Arabic equivalents. This means that the improvement was observed in the categories where L1 influence was expected to be strongest. The results therefore show that these difficult vowel categories were not fixed or resistant to change. Rather, learners were able to produce them more accurately after targeted phonetic input and feedback. This pattern is consistent with the SLM view that L2 speech learning remains possible beyond childhood, although it is shaped by the learner's previous L1 phonetic experience (Flege, 1995). In this study, the learners' previous L1 experience appeared to affect their initial production patterns, but instruction helped reduce some of these L1-based substitutions.

The stronger performance of the IPT group is also consistent with previous research on technology-mediated phonetic training. Previous studies have shown that pronunciation practice, auditory input, visual or articulatory support, and feedback can improve English segmental accuracy, particularly vowel production (Fatimah, 2021; Fouz-González, 2020; Ghounane, 2019; Haggag, 2018; Miqawati, 2020). The present findings are also in line with research in the Saudi EFL context, which has shown positive effects of mobile-assisted pronunciation training on English vowel learning and pronunciation development (Almutairi & Alghammas, 2025; Khalil, 2022). However, the present study extends this line of research in two ways. First, it focuses specifically on Hijazi Arabic-speaking learners, whose vowel system differs from English in ways that are relevant to the production of English monophthongs. Second, it interprets the vowel-specific improvement through the SLM framework, rather than only reporting overall improvement after training. The comparison between IPT and PBI also has instructional relevance. The PBI group improved from pre-test to post-test, which shows that printed phonetic materials and teacher modelling can support some development in

vowel production accuracy. However, the gains in the PBI group were smaller than those in the IPT group, especially for /ε/, /ɜ:/, /ɔ:/, /ɒ/, and /ʌ/. This difference suggests that printed materials may help learners become aware of vowel symbols and basic vowel contrasts, but they may not provide enough support for the production of difficult vowel categories. Printed explanations can describe tongue height, tongue backness, lip rounding, and vowel duration, but they cannot provide the same level of auditory comparison, visual support, or individual feedback. For vowels that are close to existing L1 categories, learners may need more than written description and teacher repetition. They may need repeated opportunities to hear the target vowel, observe its articulatory properties, produce it, and compare their production with the model.

Taken together, these findings have implications for L2 phonetics and phonology, particularly in relation to L2 vowel acquisition and L1-L2 vowel category relations. First, they support the view that English vowels without direct Hijazi Arabic equivalents are particularly difficult for Hijazi Arabic-speaking learners of English. Second, they show that these difficult vowels can improve when learners receive explicit phonetic input, articulatory support, production practice, and feedback. Third, they show that the benefit of training is not limited to vowels that were already relatively accurate before instruction. Rather, the largest gains appeared in vowels that were initially the most difficult. From an SLM perspective, this suggests that interactive phonetic training may help learners move away from L1-based substitutions and towards more accurate production of difficult L2 vowel contrasts. The findings also have practical implications for pronunciation instruction for Hijazi Arabic-speaking learners of English. Instruction should give particular attention to vowels that have no direct equivalent in Hijazi Arabic, especially /ε/, /ɜ:/, /ɔ:/, /ɒ/, and /ʌ/. These vowels should not be treated only as isolated IPA symbols or word-list items. They should be practiced through activities that connect the vowel symbol, the auditory target, the articulatory gesture, and the learner's own production. For example, learners may benefit from practice that contrasts /ε/ with /ɪ/ and /i:/, /ɜ:/ with front vowel categories, /ɔ:/ and /ɒ/ with /u:/ and /ʊ/, and /ʌ/ with /æ/. Such practice can help learners attend to the specific vowel distinctions that caused the greatest difficulty in the present study.

6. Conclusion

This study examined English monophthong production by Hijazi Arabic-speaking L2 learners through the SLM and compared the effects of mobile-based IPT and PBI on vowel production accuracy. The findings showed that learners had the greatest difficulty with vowels that do not have direct equivalents in Hijazi Arabic, which suggests L1 influence on L2 vowel

production. After instruction, the IPT group showed significantly greater improvement than the PBI group, particularly in the vowels that were least accurate at pre-test. These results indicate that mobile-based, feedback-oriented phonetic training can support more accurate production of difficult English vowel contrasts. Overall, the study contributes to L2 phonetics and phonology by linking vowel-specific production patterns and training-related improvement to the SLM framework.

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